

FOETAL DEVELOPMENT OF CAMEL HEART-A HISTOMORPHOLOGICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Gross and histological changes of 153 camel foetal hearts were investigated. The present study has shown that compartmentalization of the camel foetal heart into left and right ventricles and the left and right atria was completed by 75 days of gestation. Internally the interventricular septum, and the interatrial septae were completely formed. The formation of interatrial septum is simultaneous with the growth of interventricular septum; there was no evidence of interventricular foramen at 75 days of gestation. Furthermore, the foramen ovale persist up to the third trimester of the foetal stage of development. During first trimester cellular proliferation was recorded, which decreased toward third trimester of foetal development. The arrangement of muscle fibres in this study was from random in the first trimester to a more parallel arrangement by third trimester of pregnancy. It is concluded that the heart of camel foetus has reached a functional state of development at third trimester of pregnancy.

KEYWORDS: Camel, Heart, Histomorphological, Developmental Studies

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INTRODUCTION

Heart is the first functional organ in the developing vertebrates (Lyons, 1996) and the first embryonic organ to undergo functional differentiation (Noden and De Lahunta, 1985) as such later survival depends on its proper function (Clark, 1989). Although there are numerous studies available on heart development in domestic animals (Vitums, 1981; Noden and De Lahunta, 1985; Kwari *et al.*, 2003), little work is done on heart development in camel. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to study the morphology and histology of one humped camel (*Camelus dromedaries*) foetal heart.

Materials and methods

Sample collection

A total of 153 one humped camel (*Camelus dromedaries*) fetuses were collected as a waste from Sokoto abattoir for this study. The fetuses were collected immediately after slaughter from the uteri of the slaughtered dams.

Foetal Age Estimation

The age of the fetuses were estimated using a formula ($GA = (CVR + 23.99)/0.366$) as described by Elwishi *et al.* (1981). It was observed that out the 153 fetuses recovered 48 were in first trimester, 66 were in second trimester

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and 39 were in third trimester. In all the foetuses used for this study their abdomen had closed as it was observed that closure of the abdomen marked the end of embryonic stage (Sivachelvan., 1996).

Method of Dissection of the foetus

Each foetus was dissected proximally in-between the mandibles and continued mid-ventrally cranioposteriorly along the umbilicus to the pubic symphysis and ended at the tail. The hearts of the foetuses were then exposed carefully and removed as described by Kwari *et al.*(2003).

Gross photographs of the heart were taken. Specimens from the heart tissue sections were taken and fixed in 10% buffered formalin for one week. They were embedded in paraffin and sectioned at 5micron (μ) with Shandon AS 325 retraction microtome and dried in an oven (Drury *et al.*, 1967; Baker and Silverton, 1985; Kwari *et al.*, 2003). The slides were stained using H&E technique and examined under light microscope at 4X, 10X and 40 X objectives and appropriate photomicrographs were taken with Olympus VA NOX-T brand research microscope at 40X,100X and 400X magnifications.

RESULTS

Grossly, in the first trimester foetal heart showed indication of division in to chambers by the appearance of the grooves. Paraconal and the subsinusal interventricular grooves separating the heart into left and right ventricles and the coronary groove, separating the atria from the ventricles were clearly seen at 98 days of gestation externally (plate I) and the four chambers were seen which were more pronounced later in the third trimester (plate II). Internally all the four chambers were observed with all the septations i.e. interatrial and interventricular septae as those seen in third trimester (366 days) of gestation. The ductus arteriosus which connect aorta and pulmonary artery was seen in all the three trimesters. The foramen ovale was patent from as early as day 75 of gestation up to the late third trimester (plate III). At first trimester of gestation, the cardiac muscle fibres were arranged in a random passion in which the alignment was less parallel and many round packed cardiomyocytes were seen in the process of division (plate IV). At second trimester muscle fibres running parallel to each other with less random arrangement, cells were seen dividing (plate V). In the third trimester Myofibrils aligned more to the long axis of the cell , which were elongated and had reduced compared to first and second trimesters (plate VI).

DISCUSSION

The present study has shown that compartmentalization of the camel foetal heart into left and right ventricles and the left and right atria was completed by 75 days of gestation and this is accomplished by 5-6 weeks of gestation in Sahel goat (Kwari *et al.*, 2003) and 29 days in sheep (Brook *et al.*, 1983). Internally the interventricular septum and the interatrial septae were completely formed.

The formation of interatrial septum is simultaneous with the growth of interventricular septum; there was no evidence of interventricular foramen at 75 days of gestation. It was demonstrated that interventricular foramen closes at embryonic stage. This foramen closes at approximately 27 days of gestation in the pig and, 35 days in the horse (Noden and De Lahunta, 1985). It is also possible that the septation of the heart was completed during the embryonic stage in the camel foetus. It has been indicated that the foramen ovale remains patent throughout the foetal development in various mammals (Noden and De Lahunta, 1985) . It was also suggested that the foramen closes within minute after birth, but complete fusion takes several weeks or occasionally never occur (Noden and De Lahunta, 1985). In the present work the foramen ovale persisted up to the third trimester of the foetal stage of development.

Experimental studies have shown that the major determinant of cardiac size during prenatal development is myocyte proliferation (Clark *et al.*, 1989; Saiki *et al.*, 1997; Hu *et al.*, 2000). In this study it was observed that at first trimester there was cellular proliferation which decreased toward third trimester of foetal development. The

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arrangement of muscle fibres in this study was from random in the first to a more parallel towards third trimester of pregnancy i.e alignment towards the longitudinal axis was increasing as was reported by Hirschy *et al.* 2006 in mouse heart. The cardiomyocytes also changes from round to elongate towards late third trimester which was similar to the observation made by (Hescheler, 1997). Kwari *et al.* (2003) reported the presence of intercalated disc in 13-14 weeks foetal heart but no intercalated disc was seen in in camel fetuses collected during all the three trimester. This may probably be due the fact that no full term foetus was observed in this study. It is concluded that the heart of camel foetus has reached a functional state of development at third trimester of pregnancy.

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Plate I: External left view of 98 days old camel foetus showing four chambers of the heart and paraconal groove (arrow) which are external indicators of the separation between the two ventricles

Plate II: Heart (from left) of third trimester 350 days old camel foetus arrow showed well developed paraconal groove which are external indicators of the separation between the two ventricles at the left side

Plate III: Heart (internal right view) of third trimester (350 days old) camel foetus (arrow) entrance to cranial vena cava, **A** patent foramen ovale, **B** coronary sinus

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Plate IV: Photomicrograph of L.S of myocardium of 1st trimester (98 days) camel Foetus, the myofibrils were not well oriented, they were randomly arranged towards each other and many round cells (arrows) were seen in the process of division (H & E $\times$ 400)

Plate V: Photomicrograph of L.S. of myocardium of 2nd trimester camel foetus myofibrils were less randomly arranged towards each other and many cells were in the process of division and becoming elongated (H & E $\times$ 400)

Plate VI: Photomicrograph of L.S of myocardium of 3rd trimester (350 days old) camel foetus myofibrils aligned more to the long axis compared to the earlier trimesters and the cells had became elongated (arrows) (H & E $\times$ 400).

Abbreviations

H&E	Hematoxylin and Eosin
GA	Gestational Age
CVR	Crown Vertebral Rump
L.S	Longitudinal Section

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